

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MODERNIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article scientifically examines the role of innovative educational technologies in the modernization of higher education.

Keywords: education, modernization, innovative technologies, higher education, pedagogical skills.

РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: В статье научно исследована роль инновационных образовательных технологий в модернизации высшего образования.

Ключевые слова: образование, модернизация, инновационные технологии, высшее образование, педагогическое мастерство.

INTRODUCTION

Modern society is characterized by rapid and profound changes, and such changes are evident in public structures, including independent states, relations between individuals and society, demographic policy, and urbanization processes. Education, as a separate component of the structure of the global community, should take into account all the changes taking place in society, and change its structure and content of activity on this basis. Today, the fact that education lags behind the pace of society's development, and that the technologies used in the educational process do not fully meet modern requirements, is often recognized by the world community. Because education, as a socializer, should follow changes in society and have an impact on its development. However, the relationship between the development of society and the education system is complex and characterized by a high level of enthusiasm. Education does not accept the influence of all active and slow changes, but it has its influence on what is happening in society. From this point of view, changes in education are not only a result, but a condition for the future development of the society [1.3.].

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It is known that today, when science and technology are developing rapidly, the amount of scientific knowledge, understanding and imagination is increasing dramatically. This, on the one hand, ensures its differentiation due to the development of new fields and departments of science and technology, and on the other hand, creates the process of integration between sciences.

In such conditions, the demands for highly qualified pedagogues are increasing, capable of educating a competent generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed over the centuries, who have mastered the fundamentals of science, pedagogy and psychology methods, have a high level of professional training, and use modern pedagogical and information technologies in practice. training of creative pedagogues with skills and qualifications is required.

Currently, the wide application of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. Special attention is being paid to the systematic introduction of innovations into the field of education at the same time when the scope of pedagogical innovations is increasing and the modernization process is developing rapidly in the country. But despite the fact that many pedagogical innovations are being created, the level of introduction of pedagogical research on the implementation of new content, forms, methods and tools of teaching in educational processes cannot be considered sufficient.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In fact, in the introduction of the updated education system, it is an important requirement of today that every teacher regularly learns the innovations related to his subject and the education of the mature generation, and has the skills to apply them consistently in his work.

The formation and development of professional training of students of higher pedagogical educational institutions requires a systematic, comprehensive approach to this process. The ability of a future teacher to have deep knowledge and the ability to work effectively depends on the extent to which he has sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge of the basics of certain subjects, and the ability to effectively use information in the educational process.

It is known that today all countries are trying to introduce as many innovations as possible into education. Today's news requires an organized, planned, public approach to them. News is a long-term investment for the future. In order to arouse interest in innovation, to educate a person who strives to create new things, education itself should be rich in innovations, and the atmosphere and spirit of creativity should prevail in it. Due to such urgency, today the independent field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation is rapidly developing.

DISCUSSION

In the last years of the twentieth century, the following "crisis" situations that occurred in the field of education on a global scale were one of the main reasons for the development of "innovative" education as an alternative to "supportive" education. The following common aspects are evident in its various forms in different countries:

- 1) ensuring compatibility of social practice development needs and real training level of higher education graduates;
- 2) setting new goals in higher education institutions and the complexity of the organizational structure and forms of management;
- 3) increase in interest and opportunities of the subjects of the educational process.

The main goal of innovative education is to create a sense of responsibility for the future and self-confidence in students. The rapid development of science and development, along with the economic development of the society, is creating the basis for the emergence of fundamental differences in the content of social relations. Also, as in the economic sphere, great importance is attached to the implementation of the technological approach in the social, including the educational sphere.

"Technology" is a Greek word, "techne" means life and "logos" means teaching, science. The meaning of the term "Educational Technology" is a science and teaching that provides information in order to organize the educational system with high efficiency and creativity. At the same time, there is only one idea about the definition of mazkyp tyshyncha and its essence. There is a typical approach to the closure of the essence of Nazapiya.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that the importance of pedagogical technology is determined by the occurrence of a close connection between the newly acquired knowledge and the newly acquired knowledge. In this process, the following rules must be followed:

- equivalent (equivalent) rule of practice: the behavior of the learner in the educational environment fully corresponds to the behavior to be organized by the learner during the test or examination;
- a rule of similar practice: the learner does not have the obligation to organize the desired behavior, but has the opportunity to practice in such an environment;
- the rule for determining the result: it is used to provide the student with information on the result of the assessment of the content of his or her behavior, and in the case of a special case, to organize a final report;
- the rule of encouragement: to encourage the good behavior of the student, in the course of pedagogical activities, the student's bad behavior is not reprimanded, but practical reinforcement is given that creates the desire to improve the behavior.

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